

FEASTS- Fostering European Cellular Agriculture for Sustainable Transition Systems

Frederico Ferreira, IBB-IST, Portugal

FEASTS at a glance

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Which CM/CSF production models may provide the best impact on the food system?

Which CM/CSF product types could best serve diverse communities in the future?

Which minimum standards and criteria should define technological development and implementation to ensure that impact goals are reached?

How can safety and nutrition of CM/CSF products be fully guaranteed?

What critical knowledge do consumers and the public need for informed discussion about CM/CSF?

FEASTS at a glance

Technological Progress

CELLS

CULTURE MEDIA

BIOREACTORS

SCAFFOLDS

BIOPROCESS

FOOD FORMULATION

- ✓ Catalog of cell-types and SOPs for cell culture finalized.
- ✓ Open-access cell-lines from porcine, ovine and avian species with adipogenic and myogenic potential for use in cultured meat processes.
- ✓ Several fish cell-lines from meagre spontaneously immortalized and with differentiation potential towards muscle and fat.

Technological Progress

CELLS

CULTURE MEDIA

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FOOD FORMULATION

- ✓ Serum-free medium established with breakthrough removal one of the largest cost-driver (albumin) for plant-derived components.
- ✓ Confirmed to support bovine satellite cells culture.
- ✓ Fully described the recent research article:

Never let me down: Optimizing performance of serum free culture medium for bovine satellite cells

Lisa Schenzle, Kristina Egger, Aleksandra Fuchs, Harald Pichler

doi: <https://doi.org/10.1101/2022.11.13.516330>

Technological Progress

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FOOD FORMULATION

✓ Report of bioreactor concepts and specifications for industrial CM/CSF production underway.

Technological Progress

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FOOD FORMULATION

- ✓ Bioinks derived from algae- and plant-based materials developed for muscle- and fat tissues.
- ✓ Cytocompatible and ready to be tested with fish and bovine cells.
- ✓ Article published describing their production.

Open Access Article

3D Bioprinting of Novel κ -Carrageenan Bioinks: An Algae-Derived Polysaccharide

by Diana M. C. Marques ^{1,2} , João C. Silva ^{1,2,3} , Ana Paula Serro ^{4,5} ,
Joaquim M. S. Cabral ^{1,2} , Paola Sanjuan-Alberte ^{1,2,6,*} and Frederico C. Ferreira ^{1,2,*}

Technological Progress

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FOOD FORMULATION

✓ Bioprocess defined and designed from cell isolation to cell harvest. Inputs from industry and academic experts for adequate depiction of current technological practices.

Technological Progress

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FOOD FORMULATION

GOURMEY

Cultimate

CM/CSF food formulation matrix underway.

Catalogue of the components used for CM/CSF food formulation and their implications to product quality and organoleptic properties to be established.

Defining KPIs for CM/CSF technologies

Food Safety and Regulation

Multi stakeholder engagement

Consumer surveys:
Select 3-4 EU Countries

Living Labs:
The Netherlands
Germany
Denmark

* Individual consumers are not listed in the database; consumer groups are currently clustered under NGOs & Interest Groups

Multi stakeholder engagement

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Farmers and Aquafarmers Interviews

So far :

22 farmers interviewed coming from 5 countries (4x Germany, 6x Italy, 4 x Netherlands, 4x Poland, 4x Spain)

20 aquafarmers interviewed coming from 4 countries (3x Denmark, 2xNetherlands, 4x Norway, 11x Portugal)

Conventional meat & seafood system
(in database: 35)

* Individual consumers are not listed in the database; consumer groups are currently clustered under NGOs & Interest Groups

Thanks!

Questions Welcome!

Find more on our webpage:
<https://feasts-innovation.eu/>

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Fostering European Cellular Agriculture
for Sustainable Transition Solutions

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WP1

Project management and coordination

T1.1 Overall project coordination

T1.2 Administrative and financial management

T1.3 Data management

T1.4 Knowledge and innovation management

WP2

Stewardship model for cultured meat and cultured seafood: towards a mission-driven roadmap

T2.1 Food systems thinking approach & Mission definition

T2.2 Pre-competitive space definition: strategy outline and prioritization

T2.3 Baseline analysis and hotspot screening

T2.4 A data system design for cultured meat and seafood

T2.5 Future-proof practices towards resilient value chains

Mission-driven roadmap

WP3

Sustainability by design

T3.1 Cell sourcing and cell types

T3.2 Sustainable animal-component-free cell media and scaffolding

T3.3 Bioreactor design, scalability and decentralized production

T3.4 Process and infrastructure engineering towards circularity and minimal waste

T3.5 Food formulation, quality assessment and organoleptic properties

WP4

Multi-stakeholder engagement, socio-economic and ethical considerations

T4.1 Multi-stakeholder mapping and engagement plan

T4.2 Ethics, food justice and animal welfare

T4.3 Consumer perceptions and drivers of acceptance

T4.4 Governance of value chains and business models

T4.5 Capacitating the farmers' and aquafarmers' industry for a just transition

WP5

Food safety, nutrition and regulatory assessment

T5.1 Regulatory framework

T5.2 Food safety and liaison with EFSA

T5.3 Nutritional value and potential for custom-tailored diets

T5.4 Food labelling

WP6

Integrated and Multi-dimensional impact assessment

T6.1 Prospective life cycle assessment

T6.2 Techno-economic assessment and life cycle cost analysis

T6.3 Social life cycle assessment

T6.4 Systems Dynamic Modeling, Integrated Scenario Analysis and cost of inaction

T6.5 Integrated and comparative analysis: implications, challenges and opportunities

WP7

Communication, dissemination, exploitation and open science

T7.1 Communication and dissemination plan and engagement activities

T7.2 Synergies with relevant projects and initiatives

T7.3 Targeted actions for policy dialogue and capacity building

T7.4 Open science as a technological mission

T7.5 Exploitation strategy

WP8

Ethics Requirements

(Some) current discussion points

Valorisation need metrics and business models

- Defining Key Performance Indicators for Technology and Product
- Levels of (de)centralization, ensure equity and security
- Value created for all stakeholders

Industry needs standards

- Minimal criteria for edible cells
- Approved substances for use + Substance of concern with thresholds defined
- Sustainability metrics defined

Introduce food system thinking and stewardship model

- Interactive tool for visualising the value created through the supply chain

Innovation needs investment

- Pre-competitive knowledge for low TRL: offering open science for technological development
- Support for reaching higher TRL: Open access infrastructure to scale up and analytics for QA

Regulation to be smart, reasonable and efficient

- Support safety and nutritional
- Contribute to EU competitiveness

Consumers need information and clarity

- Labelling and certification system
- Living labs and sandboxes

Public-Private partnerships to develop the sector

- Secure investment on pre-competitive/research
- (re)Training the workforce for Food Biotechnology

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